

IMPROVEMENT OF THE ISOTACTIC PROPERTY OF POLYPROPYLENE THROUGH THE INFLUENCE OF DONORS

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Abstract. Production of isotactic polypropylene is currently an industrial demand. it is possible to reduce their atactic property through donors. in this article, the influence of donors on the reaction of obtaining polypropylene was studied.

Key words: Polyolefin, thermostabilizers, cocatalysts, stereomodifier, BUPS, plastic king.

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ИЗОТАКТИЧЕСКИХ СВОЙСТВ ПОЛИПРОПИЛЕНА ЗА СЧЕТ ВЛИЯНИЯ ДОНОРОВ

Аннотация. Производство изотактического полипропилена в настоящее время является востребованным в промышленности. уменьшить их атактическое свойство можно за счет доноров. в данной статье изучено влияние доноров на реакцию получения полипропилена.

Ключевые слова: Полиолефин, термостабилизаторы, сокатализаторы, стереомодификатор, БУПС, пластиковый король.

RESEARCH METHODS

Polypropylene is a white solid, a polymerization product of propylene, and related to the class of polyolefins. Polypropylene mainly has 3 different stereospecific types (atactic, isotactic and syndiotactic). But mainly isotactic form is produced. Polypropylene is the most widely used polymer after polyethylene, its molecular weight is from 80 to 200 thousand, and the isotactic part is from 80 to 98%.

Polypropylene ($n\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3) \rightarrow [-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-]_n$) is obtained as a result of the reaction between propylene and Sigler-Natta catalysts (TiCl_4 and AlR_3). Today, there are several types of this substance, all of which have the same formula, but differ in spatial structure: isotactic, syndiotactic and atactic. Theoretical and practical analysis of the theory of the control mechanism of isotacticity (98%) and atacticity (2%) spatial structure of polypropylene in the production of polypropylene with the help of ion-coordinating catalyst (Ziegler) and silane, as well as new modern methods and ways of obtaining syndiotactic polypropylene is the main goal. The subject of the research is that the main focus is on improving the properties of polypropylene polymer by adding a complex antioxidant, calcium stearate and local talc, and studying the theoretical basis of increasing the share of the isotactic state of polypropylene from the mechanism of action of silane.

SiSIB® PC9530 DICYCLOPENTYLDIMETHOXYSILANE (DONOR-D)

SiSIB® PC9540 ISOBUTYLISOPROPYLDIMETHOXYSILANE

Picture 1. Spatial Structure of D-Donor and BUPS Silane Controlling the Spatial Structure of Polypropylene.

Thermal stabilizers (TBM)

Various TBMs or thermostabilizers are added to composite polymer materials, including PP composites. TBM and other additives are added to the product to give it the desired properties. In order to increase the thermal stability of the composition, the following substances are used: tribasic lead sulfate (TOSS), dibasic lead stearate (DOSS), BMR-9-1 compound, calcium stearate and many similar substances. When included in the composition, they bind HCl released at high temperature, absorb it and prevent destruction.

Picture 2. Structure of calcium stearate.

Some of the TBMs added to the composition of composite polymer materials help to increase the thermal stability and reduce the intermolecular friction forces by lubricating other additives in the composition with the main polymer. There are substances that help to reduce the internal and external frictional forces for better mixing of the components in the composition preparation process. Examples of these are lubricant K-11 and stearic acid. The current scarcity and high cost of TBMs and importation from abroad imposes the obligation to create local TBMs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the research, it is planned to use theoretical chemical, physical and physicochemical methods of researching the structure and properties of polymers. In particular, the use of titrimetric analysis, elemental and X-ray structural analysis, electron microscopy, infrared spectroscopy, thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry methods is envisaged.

Polypropylene obtained under medium and low pressure is rarely used in the production of dishes and food containers. The reason for this is that low-pressure polypropylene can harm human health due to the presence of a catalyst - nickel. In autoclave reactors, homopolymer and random (6% "ethylene" is given as copolymer) polypropylene brands are determined by the configuration of the reactor system. Types of polymer brands: determined by polymer properties, feed rate, consumption of additives such as catalysts, cocatalysts, stereomodifier (silane) and

hydrogen. Hydrogen is used as a chain-link adjuster to control flow index and molecular weight distribution. Using a comonomer (ethylene) in the production of a polymer product, the obtained copolymer can exhibit high strength and excellent properties. When propylene is polymerized into polypropylene in the powder state, 58.7 kDj/mol or 1385 kDj/kg (2.4 times less than the polymerization of ethylene) heat is released. This allows the released heat to be easily removed from the reaction medium with the help of the propylene supplied to the reactor.

When turning propylene into polypropylene, the autoclave takes place in reactors at $T=70-80\text{ C}$ and $P=2.3-3\text{MPa}$ pressure. In this polymerization reaction, $\text{Ti}+4$ and $\text{Mg}+2$ complex catalysts are highly dependent on the stereoregulator, i.e. Silane, which controls the stereoregularity of the catalyst. Silane determines the spatial structure of the resulting polypropylene. As a result of the active attraction of the methoxy ($-\text{O}-\text{CH}_3$) group in the silane, it is possible to obtain isotactic or syndiotactic polypropylene. Silane plays a major role in obtaining the required mixture of isotactic (95-98%) and atactic (2-3%) polypropylene. By dissolving the resulting polypropylene in an aromatic solvent (xylene), we can determine the amount of isotactic (crystalline) and atactic (amorphous). In this case, the dissolved mass indicates the amount of atacticity (amorphous). Low cost and excellent physico-chemical properties of polypropylene contribute to the development of many industries. When it comes to the introduction of new technologies, it will be possible to increase production efficiency and replace many expensive materials with modern and advanced materials. Based on the new technology, we will be able to obtain 2 types of propylene polymerization: Homopolymer and Random polymer. In the future, it is also envisaged to receive Impact(block) polypropylene.

Picture 3. Influence of donor to polypropylene molecules.

CONCLUSION

Polypropylene has served as the basis for many modified materials, including high-strength plastics and composite thermoplastic elastomers. The new high-tech polypropylene is an environmentally friendly and easily recycled and remanufactured product. All this helps polypropylene gradually replace polyvinyl chloride, ABS plastic, polystyrene and other materials. It is widely used in all important sectors of the modern world economy: electronics, mechanical engineering, construction and many other fields. That's why polypropylene got the famous name "plastic king". And although it is not yet a leader in thermoplastics, its scope of application is gradually expanding.

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